

Step-by-step Solution of Applied Engineering Problems in Mathematics Courses Using STACK

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Introduction

- It is customary in engineering schools to incorporate mathematical knowledge and skills into engineering education.
- Solving practical problems in a mathematics course with first-year students allows them to clarify their ideas about the techniques and methods of solving problems that are necessary in their professional activities as an engineer.
- To implement the concept of practice-oriented problems, teachers of the TTK UAS and the Simon Kuznets Kharkiv National Economic University developed a set of step-by-step tasks. Each assignment translates several mathematical concepts into real practice, helping students understand the impact of these topics on their future work.
- On the other hand, a detailed approach allows the authors to control the educational actions of students in the process of studying the course material: to prompt students to effective decisions, to fix their attention on certain points of the material that students usually do not notice or misunderstand.
- STACK questions are used to ask a variety of questions while honing skills and the ability to provide quick feedback at every step.
- First-year students of Tallinn University, specializing in mathematics teacher, took part in the peer review. They gave their own idea of the concept by answering the questionnaire.

Questions Development

The screenshots show the development of several questions in the STACK system. The first question is about traffic lights and traffic volume, involving a system of linear equations. The second question is about a gas cylinder, involving integration and differentiation. The third question is about a ship's position, involving vector addition. The fourth question is about a square sheet, involving optimization. The fifth question is about a volume function, involving differentiation. The sixth question is about a vector, involving vector addition. The seventh question is about a volume function, involving differentiation. The eighth question is about a vector, involving vector addition. The ninth question is about a volume function, involving differentiation. The tenth question is about a vector, involving vector addition.

Peer Review

Q1. How satisfied are you with the step-by-step structure of the tasks?

- Not at all satisfied
- Not so satisfied
- Somewhat satisfied
- Very satisfied
- Extremely satisfied

Q2. How satisfied are you with the design of the tasks?

- Not at all satisfied
- Not so satisfied
- Somewhat satisfied
- Very satisfied
- Extremely satisfied

Q3. How difficult/easy did you find it to follow the given solution steps?

- Very difficult
- Somewhat difficult
- Neither difficult nor easy
- Somewhat easy
- Very easy

Q4. How did you handle filling in the gaps with answers?

- Very difficult
- Somewhat difficult
- Neither difficult nor easy
- Somewhat easy
- Very easy

Q5. What did you like about the tasks? Please describe at least 2 things

Q6. What did you dislike about the tasks? Please describe at least 2 things

Q7. What could be done differently?

Question 1

Question 2

Question 3

Question 4

Question 5

Guidance or step-by-step guidance
Structure
 Instant feedback when entering formulas
 Design, auxiliary drawings

Question 6

Difficulty entering math text
 Clearer division of task parts
Long scrolling
 A lot is predetermined, the desire to input more by self
 Question 7
 Could be "helpful hints"
 Add an online calculator and sketchpad

Future Plans

- Create short instructions about the STACK questions inputs syntax
- Think about how to make a student's work only computer-based (built-in online calculator, sketchpad)
- Develop a clearer design of questions according to the possibilities of STACK

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